

**POSITION-WISE ANALYSIS ON ANTHROPOMETRIC AND
BIOMECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF INTERCOLLEGIATE
HANDBALL PLAYERS**

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Abstract:

The anthropometric and biomechanical characteristics of handball players play significant roles in determining their performance, injury susceptibility, and suitability for specific positions. The purpose of the study is to analysis the role played by the playing positions with reference to the anthropometric and biomechanical characteristics of Intercollegiate Handball players. Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya intercollege Handball players were identified as the total sample as 42 Handball players by means of participation in Inter-Vidyalaya Handball Tournament organized Sri Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya (SRKV) Arts and Science College, Coimbatore held at SRKV Handball Court, from 4th and 5th August 2023. As dependent variables, anthropometric variables as Height, Weight, Skinfold Measures, Arm Length, Arm Span, Girth parameters - arm, thigh and medial calf; Width parameters - Humer and Fumerous bone width. Further, as biomechanical variables, Knee and Elbow angle, angle of ball released, Velocity of the ball were selected as variables in this study. Among 16 Wing players; 18 back positioned players and 8 pivot players as totally 48 intercollegiate Handball players were exposed for data collection on chosen criterion variables. The Statistical techniques included descriptive statistics, were applied. To find out the significant mean differences between the playing positions among the selected independent variables, Analysis of variance (ANOVA), was applied. If the F - ratio found to be significant, then to find out the pair of mean difference significant, post hoc test, scheffe's test would be utilized. Only length parameters have differences among the playing positions, by which back have greater dimensions in all length parameters, followed by pivot and wing players. The angle obtained on knee and elbow towards the Handball shot execution, against goal keeper, back players dominating the greater optimum angle followed by pivot and wing players.

Key Words: Anthropometry, Biomechanical Characteristics, Playing Positions and College Handball

Introduction:

Handball is a well-known team sport that is recognized by the International Olympic Association and is played in many different countries throughout the world. Physical and physiological characteristics of male handball players Influence of playing position and competitive level. (Tønnessen & Seiler2016). It is also performed professionally in a number of European nations. In addition, this game has become much more popular in Asia, especially in India, than many other games. According to the Association, History of Handball (2007), The dynamic, well-liked, and thrilling sport of team handball calls for athleticism, strength and endurance, agility and grace, exceptional fitness, and most importantly, teamwork. (Novica Gardasevic, et al., 2022) the study's objective was to determine the influence of morphological characteristics on throw speed in handball After ice hockey, handball is the fastest indoor sport. It's a sport in which being athletic, flamboyant, creative, and cohesive as a team is encouraged for all participants. It is one of the most popular sports in the world. It keeps us fit and healthy. Unlike all other sports, handball is a fast-paced, dynamic, and thrilling game that calls for unique movements. Physical conditioning of players should therefore be individualized and targeted to solve the position-dependent tasks during play (Haugen T., 2016). Anyone looking to have fun can play handball, which is sometimes the ultimate sport. Athletes experience constant change and excitement on the field due to the unrestricted substitutions, physical contact, penalty shots, and goal shots that can travel at top speed. After soccer, handball is one of the most popular sports in Europe and is expanding at the quickest rate in Northern Asia and Africa. German gymnastics instructors encouraged field handball as a substitute for football, especially for female athletes. Relationship between explosive performance measurements of the lower limb and repeated shuttle-sprint ability in elite adolescent handball players (Hermassi et al., 2014) The International Amateur Athletics Federation Congress established a commission to develop international team handball playing rules during a meeting in The Hague, Netherlands, in 1926. As a result, during the IX Olympic Games in Amsterdam in 1928, the International Amateur Handball

Federation (IAHF) was established. Handball was added to the Olympic Program, and Avery Brundage, a founding member of the USA, went on to become the president of the International Olympic Committee in 1933. Technical match characteristics and influence of body anthropometry on playing performance in male elite team handball (Michalsik and Aagaard 2015). The upper and lower limb heavy resistance training on the peak power, throwing velocity, and sprint performance of elite male handball players (Chelly et al., 2011).

Methods

Subjects:

The purpose of the study is to analysis the role played by the playing positions with reference to the anthropometric and biomechanical characteristics of Intercollegiate Handball players. Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya intercollege Handball players were identified as the total sample as 42 Handball players by means of participation in Inter-Vidyalaya Handball Tournament organized Sri Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya (SRKV) Arts and Science College, Coimbatore held at SRKV Handball Court, from 4th and 5th August 2023.

Procedures:

The perpendicular distance between the transverse planes of the vertex and the inferior aspects of the feet. The subject has to stand with the heels together and the heels, buttocks and upper part of the back touching the scale. The head, when placed in the Frankfort plane, need not be touching the scale. The Frankfort plane was achieved when the Orbital (lower edge of the eye socket) was in the same horizontal plane as the Tragion (notch superior to thetragus of ear).

Table 1: Selection of Anthropometric and Biomechanical Variables and Test Descriptions

Variables	Unit of Measure	Test Description	Instrument used
Height	Centimeter	Maximum distance from the floor to the highest point on the head (apex), when the subject is facing directly ahead and stands erect.	Seca Stadiometer
Weight	Kilogram	Stand erect on the weighing machine with bare foot.	Omeron Weighing Machine
Skinfold - Biceps	Millimeter	The anterior mid surface of the upper arm	Harpenden Skinfold Caliper
- Subscapula	Millimeter	Undermost tip of the inferior angle of the scapula	
- Triceps	Millimeter	The posterior surface of the upper arm	
- Supraspinale	Millimeter	Lateral section of the abdominal region	
- Abdominal	Millimeter	The 5 cm horizontally to the right hand side of the midpoint of the navel	
- Illiac Crest	Millimeter	The most inferior part of the tip to the anterior superior iliac spine	
- Front Thigh	Millimeter	The mid - point of the linear distance between the Inguinal point and the patellare.	
- Medial Calf	Millimeter	The medial aspect of the calf at the level of the maximal girth	Lufkin anthropometric tape
Arm girth relaxed	Centimeter	Circumference of the arm at the level of the mid - acromiale - radiale site	
Arm girth flexed	Centimeter	Circumference of the arm perpendicular to the long axis of the arm at the level of the peak contracted biceps brachii.	
Calf girth	Centimeter	Circumference of the leg at the level of the medial calf site.	
Arm Span	Centimeter	The measurement of the length from one end of an individual's arms (measured at the fingertips) to the other when raised parallel to the ground at shoulder height at a one-hundred eighty degree angle.	
Arm Length	Centimeter	Linear distance between the acromiale and wrist	
Leg Length	Centimeter	The vertical distance between the Trochanterion to the base of the foot	
Humerus Breadth	Centimeter	Linear distance between lateral aspect of the epicondyle and the medial aspect of the humeral Epicondyle	Campbell small bone caliper
Femur Breadth	Centimeter	Linear distance between the lateral aspect of the lateral femoral epicondyle and the medial aspect of the femoral epicondyle.	

Knee angle, Elbow angle, Angle of ball release	Degree	Angle between the (digital and proximal) two bones on the respective joint	Kinovea Software with Y1 Sports Camera (Trial Version)
Velocity of ball	Meter / Second	The displacement of the ball when it is released from the hand and hit to the target area (goal post) at the rate of seconds	
7 meters Throw Performance	Points	The accuracy of the handball throws towards the goal post against goalkeeper	Teacher Made Test

Statistical Analysis:

Mean and Standard Deviation were calculated for each variables. The relationship between the selected anthropometric variables and the coaches rating on playing ability, were tested using Pearson' product-moment correlation coefficients. Anthropometric variables that statistically correlated with performance were used to form respective linear predictive models (step-wise argument selection) with special reference to their playing positions and regional classifications. P > 00.05 was considered to be statistically significant. The data were analyzed using statistical package SPSS 15th version

Evaluation:

ISAK Accredited skin fold, anthropometric tape, weighing machine were used for the study and were periodically tested and checked the calibration. The calibrations were tested and found to be accurate enough to serve the purpose of the study. To ensure that the testers were well versed in the techniques of conducting the tests, they have number of practice sessions in the testing procedures. The error tolerance was made under the ISAK. The standardized testing protocol was used to collect the relevant data. Tester competency was evaluated together with the reliability of tests. Reliability of tests was established by test-retest process whereby consistency of results was obtained by intra class (uni-variate correlation) reliability coefficients.

Results of Descriptive Statistics:

The table 1 shows the minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation of the respective anthropometrical and biomechanical variables irrespective of their playing positions.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on Selected Anthropometric and Biomechanical Variables of Intercollegiate Handball players (N = 42)

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Height	152.1	180.8	167.187	10.8664
Weight	51.6	72.1	62.604	5.8793
Skinfold - Biceps	-.2	5.3	3.153	1.1740
Skinfold - Triceps	.2	7.0	3.409	1.7361
Skinfold - Subscapula	2.4	8.0	4.880	1.3700
Skinfold - Supraspinale	12.2	27.2	18.737	3.3934
Skinfold - Abdominal	11.8	29.8	20.374	4.1050
Skinfold - Illiac Crest	2.8	11.9	8.499	1.6894
Skinfold - Front Thigh	14.1	26.0	18.336	2.8785
Skinfold - Medial Calf	5.8	18.7	12.580	3.0003
Arm girth relaxed	12.3	35.6	24.905	4.8386
Arm girth flexed	23.6	38.2	29.780	2.9173
Calf girth	28.9	41.2	35.503	3.6409
Arm Span	164.4	194.8	179.245	9.5083
Arm Length	66.3	82.7	75.720	5.1912
Leg Length	86.5	115.0	102.598	10.3511
Humerus Breadth	3.9	8.7	6.131	.9726
Femur Breadth	4.7	12.3	8.264	1.9199
Knee Angle	94.3	130.2	114.183	10.2449
Elbow Angle	138.0	173.8	154.007	11.0791
Angle of Ball Released	22.2	29.9	26.337	1.9746
Velocity of Ball	-2.7	4.8	1.254	1.6593
7 mts Throw	-.4	2.3	.950	.6050

From the table 2, it clearly indicates that the mean and standard deviation (x;±) in all the length parameters, namely height (167.19; ±10.87), Arm Span (179.25; ±9.5), Leg Length (102.6; ±10.35) and arm length (75.72; ±5.19) were greater deviations from the mean. Their range was also have greater spread. From the table 3, position-wise descriptive statistics replicates its mean and standard deviations, possessing back players have greater value, followed by pivot and then the wing. Figure 1, Box plot reflects their range and mean height values with special reference to their playing positions namely, back, pivot and wing.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on Selected Anthropometric and Biomechanical Variables of Intercollegiate Handball players with reference to their playing positions

Variables	Playing Positions		Mean	(±) Std. Deviation
Height	Wing	16	154.2	1.4022
	Back	18	177.788	1.5814
	Pivot	8	169.311	1.2937
Weight	Wing	16	56.073	2.6055
	Back	18	65.102	1.8833
	Pivot	8	70.044	1.5836
Skinfold - Biceps	Wing	16	3.2	1.1061
	Back	18	3.379	1.3402
	Pivot	8	2.551	0.7336
Skinfold - Triceps	Wing	16	3.761	1.7064
	Back	18	3.189	1.865
	Pivot	8	3.198	1.5833
Skinfold - Subscapula	Wing	16	4.685	1.2331
	Back	18	5.054	1.4465
	Pivot	8	4.875	1.5778
Skinfold - Supraspinale	Wing	16	19.167	2.438
	Back	18	18.803	4.3476
	Pivot	8	17.731	2.686
Skinfold - Abdominal	Wing	16	20.495	5.3133
	Back	18	19.85	3.5738
	Pivot	8	21.311	2.3329
Skinfold - Iliac Crest	Wing	16	8.145	1.5178
	Back	18	8.568	1.8966
	Pivot	8	9.052	1.5481
Skinfold - Front Thigh	Wing	16	18.37	2.822
	Back	18	18.783	3.0991
	Pivot	8	17.264	2.5122
Skinfold - Medial Calf	Wing	16	12.705	3.063
	Back	18	13.087	2.8902
	Pivot	8	11.19	3.0708
Arm girth relaxed	Wing	16	25.699	4.5702
	Back	18	26.322	4.3217
	Pivot	8	20.131	3.7902
Arm girth flexed	Wing	16	29.704	2.7399
	Back	18	29.929	3.2734
	Pivot	8	29.593	2.762
Calf girth	Wing	16	36.422	3.6611
	Back	18	34.406	3.2355
	Pivot	8	36.13	4.2453
Arm Span	Wing	16	169.81	2.5409
	Back	18	189.593	2.3779
	Pivot	8	174.833	0.9464
Arm Length	Wing	16	69.763	2.7488
	Back	18	79.972	1.5787
	Pivot	8	78.068	1.3032
Leg Length	Wing	16	89.818	1.6278
	Back	18	110.397	2.6857
	Pivot	8	110.61	1.1314
Humerus Breadth	Wing	16	6.24	0.7925
	Back	18	5.912	0.9806
	Pivot	8	6.404	1.2739
Femur Breadth	Wing	16	8.395	1.811
	Back	18	7.929	1.7854
	Pivot	8	8.758	2.4925
Knee Angle	Wing	16	125.637	3.6539

	Back	18	110.176	2.4326
	Pivot	8	100.292	3.1769
Elbow Angle	Wing	16	167.076	2.4672
	Back	18	143.756	3.5277
	Pivot	8	150.935	2.0811
	Wing	16	27.106	1.9661
Angle of Ball Released	Back	18	25.773	1.6869
	Pivot	8	26.065	2.3211
Velocity of Ball	Wing	16	1.155	2.0695
	Back	18	1.141	1.3755
	Pivot	8	1.704	1.4378
	Wing	16	0.751	0.482
7 mts Throw	Back	18	1.008	0.6427
	Pivot	8	1.218	0.6792

From the figure 1, the minimum and maximum range were explored the height of Intercollegiate Handball players with reference to their playing positions.

Figure 1: Box Plot on Height with reference to Playing Positions - Wing, Back and Pivot

Table 4: Analysis of variance on selected Anthropometric variables among Wing (W); Back (B) and Pivot (P) of Intercollegiate Handball Players

Dependent Variable	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Height	Between Groups	4757.522	2	2378.761	1108.107	.000
	Within Groups	83.721	39	2.147		
Weight	Between Groups	1237.521	2	618.760	134.302	.000
	Within Groups	179.682	39	4.607		
Skinfold - Biceps	Between Groups	3.852	2	1.926	1.427	.252
	Within Groups	52.655	39	1.350		
Skinfold - Triceps	Between Groups	3.216	2	1.608	.521	.598
	Within Groups	120.357	39	3.086		
Skinfold - Subscapula	Between Groups	1.153	2	.577	.297	.745
	Within Groups	75.802	39	1.944		
Skinfold - Abdominal	Between Groups	12.212	2	6.106	.351	.706
	Within Groups	678.678	39	17.402		
Skinfold - Iliac Crest	Between Groups	4.538	2	2.269	.787	.462
	Within Groups	112.483	39	2.884		
Skinfold - Front Thigh	Between Groups	12.817	2	6.408	.765	.472
	Within Groups	326.902	39	8.382		

Skinfold - Medial Calf	Between Groups	20.326	2	10.163	1.137	.331
	Within Groups	348.747	39	8.942		
Arm girth relaxed	Between Groups	228.536	2	114.268	6.093	.005
	Within Groups	731.373	39	18.753		
Arm girth flexed	Between Groups	.773	2	.386	.043	.958
	Within Groups	348.163	39	8.927		
Calf girth	Between Groups	38.335	2	19.168	1.480	.240
	Within Groups	505.182	39	12.953		
Arm Span	Between Groups	3507.499	2	1753.750	343.295	.000
	Within Groups	199.235	39	5.109		
Arm Length	Between Groups	937.314	2	468.657	109.058	.000
	Within Groups	167.596	39	4.297		
Leg Length	Between Groups	4221.649	2	2110.824	480.490	.000
	Within Groups	171.330	39	4.393		
Humerus Breadth	Between Groups	1.651	2	.825	.867	.428
	Within Groups	37.130	39	.952		
Femur Breadth	Between Groups	4.253	2	2.127	.565	.573
	Within Groups	146.875	39	3.766		

* Significant at F table (0.05, df(2,39)) = 3.23

In table 4, the results of one-way analysis of variance on selected anthropometric variables of Intercollegiate Handball players with reference to their playing positions namely Wing, Back and Pivot were presented. From the table it can be seen that the calculated F value of all the anthropometric variables on Height; Weight; Arm Girth Relaxed; Arm Span; Arm Length and Leg Length were greater than the table value of 3.23, indicating that there was a significant mean differences exists ($p < 0.05$) at degree of freedom (2, 39) at 0.05 level of significance. Since the F value was significant, the Scheffe's Post-hoc test was further computed to find out which pair of group is high among the others and the results are presented in the table 5.

Table 5: Scheffe's post-hoc test for mean differences between the Wing (W); Back (B) and Pivot (P) of Anthropometric Characteristics among Intercollegiate Handball Players

Dependent Variable	(I) Playing Positions	(J) Playing Positions	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Height	Wing	Back	-23.5879*	0.5034	0
		Pivot	-15.1110*	0.6344	0
	Back	Wing	23.5879*	0.5034	0
		Pivot	8.4769*	0.6226	0
	Pivot	Wing	15.1110*	0.6344	0
		Back	-8.4769*	0.6226	0
Weight	Wing	Back	-9.0288*	0.7375	0
		Pivot	-13.9704*	0.9294	0
	Back	Wing	9.0288*	0.7375	0
		Pivot	-4.9416*	0.9121	0
	Pivot	Wing	13.9704*	0.9294	0
		Back	4.9416*	0.9121	0
Arm girth relaxed	Wing	Back	-0.6222	1.4879	0.916
		Pivot	5.5682*	1.8752	0.019
	Back	Wing	0.6222	1.4879	0.916
		Pivot	6.1904*	1.8401	0.007
	Pivot	Wing	-5.5682*	1.8752	0.019
		Back	-6.1904*	1.8401	0.007
Arm Span	Wing	Back	-19.7829*	0.7766	0
		Pivot	-5.0225*	0.9787	0
	Back	Wing	19.7829*	0.7766	0
		Pivot	14.7604*	0.9604	0
	Pivot	Wing	5.0225*	0.9787	0
		Back	-14.7604*	0.9604	0
Arm Length	Wing	Back	-10.2090*	0.7123	0
		Pivot	-8.3051*	0.8976	0
	Back	Wing	10.2090*	0.7123	0
		Pivot	1.9039	0.8809	0.11
	Pivot	Wing	8.3051*	0.8976	0

		Back	-1.9039	0.8809	0.11
Leg Length	Wing	Back	-20.5790*	0.7202	0
		Pivot	-20.7921*	0.9076	0
	Back	Wing	20.5790*	0.7202	0
		Pivot	-0.213	0.8906	0.972
	Pivot	Wing	20.7921*	0.9076	0
		Back	0.213	0.8906	0.972

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

In table 6, the Scheffe's Post-hoc test indicated that the back and wing pair of mean difference is high in all the significantly differed anthropometric variables. From that it can be clearly noticed that there was a significant mean difference between the back and the wing players, having the maximum values followed by back and pivot players and then the wing and pivot players on anthropometric variables of position-wise Handball players.

Table 6: Analysis of variance on selected Biomechanical variables among Wing (W); Back (B) and Pivot (P) of Intercollegiate Handball Players

Dependent Variable	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Knee Angle	Between Groups	3931.758	2	1965.879	206.369	.000
	Within Groups	371.516	39	9.526		
Elbow Angle	Between Groups	4699.472	2	2349.736	275.047	.000
	Within Groups	333.178	39	8.543		
Angle of Ball Released	Between Groups	15.782	2	7.891	2.136	.132
	Within Groups	144.074	39	3.694		
Velocity of Ball	Between Groups	2.007	2	1.004	.353	.705
	Within Groups	110.880	39	2.843		
7 mts Throw	Between Groups	1.271	2	.635	1.804	.178
	Within Groups	13.735	39	.352		

* Significant at F table (0.05, df(2,39)) = 3.23

In table 7, the results of one-way analysis of variance on biomechanical variables among the three groups namely wing, back and pivot were presented. From the table it can be seen that the calculated F value of Knee and Elbow angle (F = 206.37 & 275.05) respectively among the three groups was greater than the table value of 3.23, indicating that it was significant (p < 0.05) for the degrees of freedom (2, 39) at 0.05 level of significance. Since the F value was significant, the Scheffe's Post-hoc test was further computed to find out which pair of group is high among the others and the results are presented in the table 8.

Table 8: Scheffe's post-hoc test for mean differences between the Wing (W); Back (B) and Pivot (P) of Biomechanical Characteristics among Intercollegiate Handball Players

Dependent Variable	(I) Playing Positions	(J) Playing Positions	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Knee Angle	Wing	Back	15.4610*	1.0605	.000
		Pivot	25.3448*	1.3365	.000
	Back	Wing	-15.4610*	1.0605	.000
		Pivot	9.8838*	1.3115	.000
	Pivot	Wing	-25.3448*	1.3365	.000
		Back	-9.8838*	1.3115	.000
Elbow Angle	Wing	Back	23.3193*	1.0043	.000
		Pivot	16.1405*	1.2656	.000
		Back	-23.3193*	1.0043	.000
	Back	Pivot	-7.1788*	1.2420	.000
		Wing	-16.1405*	1.2656	.000
	Pivot	Back	7.1788*	1.2420	.000

In table 8, the Scheffe's Post-hoc test indicated that the wing and back pair of mean difference is high than the other pair of mean differences in Knee and Elbow angle. From that it can be clearly noticed that there was a significant mean difference exists between the back and wing and having the maximum values followed by back and pivot players of position-wise Handball players.

Discussion on Findings:

Positional play is fundamental to the success of a handball team. It's not just about individual skill but also about how well players work together within their assigned positions to achieve common objectives. In modern Handball, tremendous rules as well as dimensions have been modified have had significant influences on Handball players' playing ability, specifically with reference to their playing positions. The role played by each position has been varied in nature according to their skill

characteristics. Relationships between power and strength of the upper and lower limb muscles and throwing velocity in male handball players (Chelly and Hermassi 2010). This is what depicted in the result of the study. Analysis of variance clearly shows that there is a significant difference exists on their respective anthropometric and skill related characteristics. Among which, back players having maximum dimensions, followed by wing and then the pivot players in case of skill profile of the Intercollegiate Handball players. Anthropometry and body composition of female handball players according to competitive level or the playing position (Chiara 2011). Further, it is interesting to note that the biomechanical variables, the back players dominated maximum dimensions, followed by wing and then the pivot. The Differences in physical fitness and throwing velocity among elite and amateur female handball players (Granados 2007). Back players need strong upper body muscles, especially in the shoulders and arms, to generate power and accuracy in their shots. Biomechanically, this involves proper shoulder rotation, elbow extension, and wrist snap to propel the ball with force and precision towards the goal. Wings must be able to shoot accurately while on the move or from difficult angles. Biomechanically, this requires good coordination of upper body movements, including shoulder rotation, arm extension, and wrist snaps, to generate power and accuracy in shots. Anthropometric, physiological and performance characteristics of elite team-handball players (Chaouachi 2009). Pivots frequently engage in post-up moves to receive passes with their back to the goal and create scoring opportunities for themselves or teammates. Biomechanically, this involves proper footwork, body positioning, and coordination of movements to establish leverage against defenders and execute spinning or turning maneuvers to evade pressure and score. Biomechanical characteristics highlight the diverse physical demands and skill requirements of each position in handball, emphasizing the importance of specialized training to optimize performance in specific roles.

Conclusions:

The role played by the playing positions namely wing, back and pivot is not same and they providing a distinct advantage in playing specific positions by means of size, shape and structure of the Handball players. Only length parameters have differences among the playing positions, by which back have greater dimensions in all length parameters, followed by pivot and wing players. Among the girth, breadth and circumference dimensions, the playing positions in Handball remains same characteristics and acknowledge no meaningful size differences.

The angle obtained on knee and elbow towards the Handball shot execution, against goal keeper, back players dominating the greater optimum angle followed by pivot and wing, revealed that adopting scientific technique along with greater size, shape and structure, are more essential specifically acquiring biomechanical characteristics.

Practical Applications:

Anthropometric and biomechanical characteristics play significant roles in handball, both in understanding player performance and injury prevention. Anthropometric data, such as height, arm length, and hand size, can influence a player's suitability for different positions on the handball court. Coaches use this information to strategically position players based on their physical attributes, maximizing team performance. Injury Prevention and Rehabilitation Biomechanical assessment can identify biomechanical risk factors for common handball injuries, such as shoulder impingement, knee ligament injuries, and ankle sprains. By addressing biomechanical deficiencies through targeted training and conditioning programs, coaches and medical staff can reduce the likelihood of injuries and promote faster rehabilitation. Biomechanical analysis helps in evaluating the impact of equipment design on player biomechanics, such as grip stability and joint loading during throwing and catching. Biomechanical assessment techniques, such as motion capture and video analysis, enable coaches to evaluate player performance objectively. By quantifying parameters such as throwing velocity, jump height, and agility, coaches can identify talented players, monitor skill development, and tailor training interventions accordingly. Biomechanical Feedback and Coaching, Real-time biomechanical feedback systems, such as wearable sensors and motion analysis software, provide coaches and players with immediate insights into movement mechanics during training and competition. Accuracy and throwing velocity in handball (Bayio 1996). This feedback allows for adjustments in technique and training drills to optimize performance and reduce injury risk. Overall, anthropometric and biomechanical characteristics are essential considerations in handball for optimizing performance, reducing injury risk, and enhancing the overall experience for players and coaches alike.

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